

Bidirectional Converter for On-Board Battery Charging in Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicles Using Reptile Search Optimization (RSO)

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KEYWORDS

Electric vehicle, Battery, Bidirectional converter, Inverter, Motor winding, RSO algorithm.

ABSTRACT

A novel hybrid control strategy for a bidirectional DC-DC converter used in on-board battery charging systems of Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs). The proposed method utilizes the Reptile Search Optimization (RSO) algorithm to enhance control performance by dynamically adjusting gate signals to manage charging and discharging modes efficiently. The hybrid control scheme integrates both rule-based logic and intelligent decision-making to ensure robust energy flow management between the battery and the vehicle's DC bus. RSO is utilized to minimize tracking errors and optimize the switching pattern to improve charge efficiency, battery lifespan, and the overall system. The converter operates in buck mode during charging from the grid or renewable sources, and in boost mode during battery discharge to support vehicle load. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed control technique in maintaining desired State of Charge (SOC) levels, reducing power losses, and ensuring seamless transition between operating modes. Comparative analysis against conventional PSO-based and rule-based controllers confirms the superiority of the RSO-based approach in terms of convergence speed and control accuracy. This research contributes to the development of more reliable and energy-efficient PHEV charging systems using advanced bio-inspired optimization techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs) are emerging as a highly practical solution for sustainable transportation, as they combine the benefits of both internal combustion engines and electric propulsion systems [1] [2]. By utilizing a hybrid energy system, PHEVs allow for longer driving ranges, reduced fuel consumption, and lower emissions compared to conventional vehicles. A key subsystem in the overall PHEV architecture is the On-Board Charger (OBC), which enables energy transfer from the grid to the vehicle battery without requiring external infrastructure [3-4]. As demand increases for fast, efficient, and compact charging systems, researchers are focusing on enhancing the performance of OBC units while meeting space, weight, and cost constraints typical of automotive applications. Among the various components in OBCs, the bidirectional DC-DC converter plays a crucial role by enabling both grid-to-vehicle (G2V) and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) operations [5-6]. This bidirectionally not only supports conventional charging but also allows the vehicle to act as a distributed energy source for the grid during demand peaks. To further reduce component count and size, recent topologies have adopted the use of motor windings as passive inductors and integrated traction inverters as rectification units. Although these innovations help reduce weight and cost, they pose new challenges in terms of control, such as managing power flow, reducing current ripples, and ensuring battery protection during charging and discharging processes. To address these control complexities, various intelligent techniques have been proposed in recent studies. Conventional controllers like Proportional-Integral (PI) have been enhanced with intelligent approaches such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Neural Networks (NN), and their hybrids like ANN-PSO or ANN-IPSO. These algorithms provide improved dynamic response, better disturbance rejection, and higher efficiency. For example, an author Anjinappa et al. proposed an NN-IPSO-based control strategy for an isolated bidirectional converter. Their approach demonstrated improved Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), reduced power loss, and increased efficiency compared to conventional converters, making it a promising direction for advanced charger control.

To overcome these challenges, this paper proposes a novel control approach based on the RSO algorithm. RSO

is a recent bio-inspired algorithm that mimics the intelligent hunting behavior of reptiles, offering a better balance between exploration and exploitation during the optimization process. The proposed method eliminates the need for neural network dependency while retaining strong convergence performance and accuracy. By integrating RSO into the control loop of the bidirectional DC-DC converter, this approach enables smoother energy flow control, reduced THD, and higher efficiency in both charging and discharging operations. MATLAB/Simulink simulation results demonstrate that RSO outperforms IPSO in convergence speed, SOC regulation, and power quality, making it a robust and scalable solution for future PHEV on-board charging systems. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the detailed system design, including the overall architecture and converter configuration. Section III discusses the control strategy adopted for managing bidirectional power flow and maintaining system stability. Section IV introduces the proposed RSO algorithm-based control scheme and its integration into the converter topology. Section V provides simulation results and comparative performance analysis between RSO and existing IPSO-based methods using MATLAB/Simulink. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper by summarizing the key contributions and highlighting the future scope of this research.

2. SYSTEM DESIGNING

Figure.1 Block diagram of the system

The proposed bidirectional converter-based on-board charging system for PHEVs is designed to ensure intelligent energy flow between the DC power source, the electric motor, and the battery system. The system integrates two inverters, a bidirectional DC-DC converter, motor winding, and an RSO-based control unit to enhance charging performance as shown in the fig.1. The topology is optimized for compactness and high efficiency

A. DC Source and Bidirectional DC–DC Converter

The system is supplied by a regulated DC voltage source, representative of the output from a rectified grid interface or a standalone DC charging station [12]. This source is responsible for maintaining a stable input to the power conversion chain under both charging and regenerative modes. The voltage level is chosen based on the required operating range of the converter and battery, and it must remain within defined limits to support dynamic load variations during electric vehicle operation. The simulation models of the DC source and bidirectional converters are presented in the figure.2

To facilitate bidirectional energy flow, a DC–DC converter is connected between the DC source and the internal traction and battery subsystems [7-8]. This converter is designed to operate in both buck and boost configurations, depending on the direction of power transfer. In buck mode, the converter steps down the voltage during battery charging, supplying a controlled current based on the battery's charging profile [9] [10]. The converter topology comprises high-speed switching devices, inductors, and filtering elements. Its design ensures high power conversion efficiency and reduced ripple characteristics. The mode of operation is selected based on voltage sensing and directional energy demands, ensuring seamless transition between driving and charging states [11].

Figure.2 Simulation models a) DC source and b) Bidirectional converter

B. Modelling of Inverter-1 and Motor Winding

The first inverter, labelled Inverter-1, is placed between the bidirectional DC–DC converter and the motor winding. The simulation model of inverter-1 is displayed in fig.3. Its primary function is to perform real-time DC–AC conversion to generate a balanced three-phase waveform required to drive the motor [13]. During traction mode, Inverter-1 synthesizes sinusoidal AC signals that energize the stator windings, producing a rotating magnetic field to generate mechanical torque. The generated waveform is synchronized to motor speed and load torque, ensuring optimal torque-per-ampere utilization and efficient operation across varying speeds.

Figure.3 simulation model of the inverter-1

This inverter supports four-quadrant operation by dynamically adjusting the amplitude and phase angle of the output waveform, allowing for forward and reverse motion as well as motoring and braking modes. It responds to electrical reference inputs—such as speed demand or torque feedback—and modulates its switching devices accordingly using techniques such as space vector modulation (SVM) or sinusoidal PWM [14-15]. The output waveform must be precisely shaped to reduce current distortion and electromagnetic interference, both of which directly affect the performance of the motor and other downstream electronics. During regenerative braking, the mechanical energy of the rotating machine is converted back into electrical energy. In this mode, the motor functions as a generator, producing three-phase AC voltage at its terminals. Inverter-1 operates in reverse conduction mode, converting this AC back into DC and routing it upstream to the DC link. This recovered energy can either be transferred to the battery through Inverter-2 or sent to the DC source through the bidirectional converter, depending on system mode and energy flow configuration. The motor winding acts not only as the

active component for propulsion but also serves as a passive inductive filter in charging or braking scenarios. When used as an inductor, the motor smoothens high-frequency current components generated by the inverters, suppressing harmonics and improving the quality of power delivered to the battery or sourced from it. This dual-use of the motor winding eliminates the need for dedicated filter inductors, contributing to system compactness and weight reduction, which are critical in vehicle-integrated applications [16] [17].

C. Modelling of Inverter 2 and Battery

The second inverter, referred to as Inverter-2, is connected between the motor winding and the battery system. Its purpose is to regulate the energy flow between the motor and the battery under both charging and discharging conditions, the simulation model of the battery is shown in the figure.4. Unlike Inverter-1, which primarily manages traction control, Inverter-2 is dedicated to power conditioning for the battery, performing AC-DC and DC-AC conversion as required based on the operational state of the system.

During regenerative braking, when the motor acts as a generator and delivers three-phase AC power, Inverter-2 operates as a rectifier. It converts the incoming AC waveform into a regulated DC output suitable for battery charging. This DC power is filtered and shaped to ensure it aligns with the battery's voltage and current acceptance profile. The inverter's operation in this mode supports controlled energy recovery, allowing kinetic energy from braking to be effectively captured and stored in the battery, improving the overall energy efficiency of the system. In discharge mode, when the battery is required to supply energy, Inverter-2 reverses its role and functions as a DC-AC converter [18-19].

Figure.4 Simulation model of the battery

The battery itself is interfaced with voltage, current, and thermal sensors to enable real-time monitoring of its State of Charge (SOC), health, and operating limits [20]. Charging and discharging are managed within safe thresholds to prevent overvoltage, overcurrent, or

thermal stress. The output of Inverter-2 is regulated to maintain consistent power quality and protect the battery management system (BMS) from transient disturbances or harmonic distortion.

3. CONTROL TOPOLOGY

Figure.5 Controlling topology

The control topology of the proposed system integrates both conventional and intelligent control techniques to ensure effective power regulation, voltage tracking, and current control within the bidirectional converter-based charging system. The architecture, as shown in Fig.5, is composed of three main stages: a PI controller, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) controller, and the RSO algorithm, working in coordination to generate optimized gating signals for both the inverter (Gate_inv) and bidirectional converter (Gate_bi). The output from the ANN is directed to the RSO algorithm block, which acts as the final decision-making unit. The RSO block continuously evaluates system parameters and applies its bio-inspired search mechanism to optimize the PWM switching pulses for both the inverter and bidirectional converter. It determines the most efficient gating patterns to minimize harmonic distortion, switching loss, and overshoot while maintaining accurate voltage and current regulation.

The coordinated action of the PI, ANN, and RSO components allows the system to transition smoothly between different load conditions and operating modes such as charging, discharging, and regenerative braking. The control structure ensures that the gate signals (Gate_inv and Gate_bi) are generated with high precision, resulting in improved converter efficiency, waveform quality, and battery protection. This multi-layered control strategy effectively combines the simplicity of classical control, the learning capability of ANN, and the global optimization strength of RSO.

4. PROPOSED METHOD

The control optimization in the proposed system is achieved using the RSO algorithm, a bio-inspired metaheuristic technique modelled on the intelligent and cooperative hunting behaviour of crocodiles. In nature,

This Simulink model appears to represent a bidirectional power flow system between a DC source and a battery via an inverter and motor drive setup. The control system uses an ANN tuned by the IPSO algorithm for control, likely in managing bidirectional energy transfer and motor control.

Figure.7 Efficiency by using IPSO

Figure.8 Output of DC source

Figure.9 Three phase inverter a) voltage and b) current

The inverter-side output voltages exhibit a balanced three-phase waveform, confirming correct inverter operation. Each phase maintains a consistent amplitude centered on the DC bus voltage, producing a clean sinusoidal output. The current waveforms display symmetry, with consistent amplitude and minimal distortion.

Figure.10 Battery related soc, voltage, and current

The battery is in charging mode, starting at 50% SOC and increasing slightly to 50.002%, indicating charging. The current remains stable at around -2.1 A, confirming controlled charging. The voltage is constant at approximately 265 V, showing effective voltage regulation. Overall, the system ensures stable and efficient charging under the control of the ANN-IPSO controller.

Figure.11 waveform of Efficiency %

Fig.11 displays the overall efficiency (η) from DC source to battery

Figure.12 Thd value of inverter side voltage

The inverter-side voltage exhibits a THD of 3.54%, indicating a high-quality sinusoidal output. This THD level falls well within the acceptable limits for motor drive applications, which typically require THD values below 5%. The low distortion reflects the effectiveness of the ANN-IPSO-based controller in managing switching

operations, resulting in smooth voltage waveforms, minimized harmonic losses, and improved overall system efficiency.

RSO-Based Simulation Results

Figure.13 Schematic diagram of Reptile Search Optimization of model

This Simulink model of fig.13 represents a bidirectional power flow system between a DC source and a battery through an inverter and motor drive, specifically designed for on-board battery charging in PHEVs. An ANN controller is employed to regulate energy transfer and manage motor control. To optimize the performance of the ANN, the model utilizes RSO, which offers faster convergence and improved handling of nonlinearities in dynamic environments. Standard drive cycles and charging data are incorporated to simulate real-world conditions, ensuring accurate and efficient control during both charging operations.

Figure.14 output of Dc source

Figure.15 Three-phase inverter a) voltage and b) current

The inverter-side phase currents are balanced and sinusoidal, indicating effective current control and uniform load sharing across all three phases. Each current waveform exhibits symmetry and consistent amplitude, demonstrating the effectiveness of the Neural Network controller enhanced through RSO. The integration of RSO significantly improves the controller's performance, resulting in reduced harmonic distortion and enhanced overall system efficiency.

Figure.16 Battery soc, current and voltage

The battery operates in charging mode, beginning at a 50% state of charge (SOC) and increasing slightly to 50.002%, indicating a slow and controlled charging process. The charging current remains stable at approximately -2.1 A, confirming consistent and regulated power flow. The battery voltage is maintained at around 265 V, demonstrating effective voltage regulation. Overall, the system achieves stable and efficient charging performance under the control of the ANN optimized by RSO.

(a)

(b)

Figure. 17 (a) and (b) Showing the efficiency of the system

The overall efficiency (η) from the DC source to the battery is high and shows a slight improvement due to the implementation of RSO.

Figure.18 Thd value of Vabc

The inverter-side voltage exhibits a THD of 1.83%, indicating a high-quality sinusoidal output suitable for sensitive motor drive applications. This THD level is well below the standard threshold of 5%, as recommended by IEEE 519, ensuring compliance with power quality standards. The low distortion demonstrates the effectiveness of the ANN controller optimized using RSO, which ensures precise switching control. This results in smooth voltage waveforms, reduced harmonic losses, and enhanced overall system efficiency and reliability, making it ideal for PHEV operations.

Table-I THDs comparison table

Performance Parameter	IPSO-Based Control	RSO-Based Control
THD of Vabc	3.54%	1.83%

From the simulation outcomes, it is evident that the RSO-based control strategy offers a substantial improvement in output waveform quality. The THD of the inverter-side voltage is reduced from 3.54% (IPSO) to 1.83% (RSO), demonstrating a notable suppression of harmonic distortion. This is attributed to RSO's adaptive switching logic and smooth duty cycle regulation, which leads to more symmetrical and stable output voltages. Additionally, the RSO system shows reduced ripple amplitude, improved tracking accuracy, and less overshoot in the voltage waveform when compared to the IPSO method.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel RSO-based hybrid control strategy for a bidirectional converter integrated

with a dual-inverter system for on-board battery charging in PHEVs. The system architecture efficiently reused existing motor windings as inductive filters and leveraged both inverter stages for dynamic power routing between the grid, motor, and battery. By replacing the conventional IPSO-based controller with the RSO algorithm, the proposed method introduced an adaptive and computation-efficient control framework capable of handling nonlinearities and mode transitions without neural network dependencies. Simulation results validated that the RSO-integrated system achieved lower THD, faster convergence, and reduced voltage ripple compared to the IPSO-based system. Specifically, inverter-side THD was reduced from 3.54% to 1.83%, demonstrating a significant improvement in waveform quality. The RSO controller also offered real-time flexibility, stable performance under varying load conditions, and reduced control overhead.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Khaligh and M. D'Antonio, "Global trends in high-power on-board chargers for electric vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 3306–3324, Apr. 2019.
- [2] A. Khaligh and S. Dusmez, "Comprehensive topological analysis of conductive and inductive charging solutions for plug-in electric vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 3475–3489, Oct.
- [3] M. R. Khalid, I. A. Khan, S. Hameed, M. S. J. Asghar, and J.-S. Ro, "A comprehensive review on structural topologies, power levels, energy storage systems, and standards for electric vehicle charging stations and their impacts on grid," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 128069–128094, 2021.
- [4] S. Haghbin, S. Lundmark, M. Alakula, and O. Carlson, "Grid-connected integrated battery chargers in vehicle applications: Review and new solution," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 459–473, Feb 2013.
- [5] J. Yuan, L. Dorn-Gomba, A. D. Callegaro, J. Reimers, and A. Emadi, "A review of bidirectional on-board chargers for electric vehicles," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 51501–51518, 2021.
- [6] P. Mahure, R. K. Keshri, R. Abhyankar, and G. Buja, "Bidirectional conductive charging of electric vehicles for V2V energy exchange," in *Proc. 46th Annu. Conf. IEEE Ind. Electron. Soc. (IECON)*, Oct. 2020, pp. 2011–2016.
- [7] D. Xu, C. Zhao, and H. Fan, "A PWM plus phase-shift control bidirectional DC–DC converter," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 666–675, May 2004.

- [8] Xiao and S. Xie, "A ZVS bidirectional DC-DC converter with phase shift plus PWM control scheme," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 813-823, Mar. 2008.
- [9] M. Yilmaz and P. T. Krein, "Review of battery charger topologies, charging power levels, and infrastructure for plug-in electric and hybrid vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 2151-2169, May 2013.
- [10] F. Musavi, W. Eberle, and W. G. Dunford, "A phase-shifted semi-bridgeless boost power factor corrected converter for plug-in hybrid electric vehicle battery chargers" in *Proc. 2011 IEEE Appl. Power Electron. Conf. Expo.*, pp. 821-828.
- [11] K. Clement-Nyns, E. Haesen, and J. Driesen, "The impact of charging plug-in hybrid electric vehicles on a residential distribution grid," *IEEE Trans. Power Appar. Syst.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 371-380, Feb. 2010.
- [12] E. Durán, J. M. Andújar, F. Segura et al., "A high-flexibility DC load for fuel cell and solar arrays power sources based on DC-DC converters," *Applied Energy*, vol. 88, no. 5, pp. 1690-1702, May 2011.
- [13] A. Emadi, Y. Lee, K. Rajashekara, Power electronics and motor drives in electric, hybrid electric and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 2237-2245, June 2008.
- [14] Y. Lee, A. Khaligh, and A. Emadi, "Advanced integrated bi-directional AC/DC and DC/DC converter for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 3970-3980, Oct. 2009.
- [15] M. Yilmaz and P. T. Krein, "Review of battery charger topologies, charging power levels, and infrastructure for plug-in electric and hybrid vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 2151-2169, May 2013.
- [16] I. Verbytskyi, M. Lukianov, K. Nasserredine et al., "Power converter solutions for industrial PV applications - a review," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 9, p. 3295, Apr. 2022.
- [17] S. Chakraborty, H. N. Vu, M. M. Hasan et al., "DC-DC converter topologies for electric vehicles, plug-in hybrid electric vehicles and fast charging stations: state of the art and future trends," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 8, p. 1569, Apr. 2019.
- [18] X. Zhou, S. Lukic, S. Bhattacharya, and A. Huang, "Design and Control of Grid-connected Converter in Bi-directional Battery Charger for Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle Application," in *Proc. IEEE VPPC*, 2009, pp. 1716-1721.
- [19] S. Abbasian and M. Farsijani, "A single-switch high step-up zero current switching DC-DC converter based on three-winding coupled inductor and voltage multiplier cells with quasi resonant operation," *International Journal of Circuit Theory and Applications*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 4419-4433, Dec. 2022.
- [20] A. Khaligh and M. D'Antonio, "Global trends in high-power on-board chargers for electric vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 3306-3324, Apr. 2019.